

Extension of multi-signature based privacy-ABC system with commit-and-prove techniques

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Abstract

The increasing user awareness and regulatory framework (e.g., GDPR) have contributed to considering data minimization and privacy-by-design as central guiding principles for new systems. Among others, this has led to a paradigm shift towards Self-Sovereign Identity solutions to put the user in full control over their data. Despite the promising landscape, privacy-preserving Attribute-Based Credentials (p-ABC) have not been widely adopted, mainly due to the lack of secure, flexible and efficient implementations that cover the basic and advanced needs in p-ABC systems. In this work, we tackle this gap by formalizing an improved zero-knowledge showing protocol of a distributed p-ABC scheme based on Pointcheval-Sanders Multi-Signatures to allow for modular extensions through commit-and-prove techniques. We use it to implement a flexible p-ABC system with decentralized issuance that, apart from the basic notions of p-ABCs, covers range proofs, pseudonyms, inspection and revocation. Lastly, we thoroughly evaluate the performance of the system under different testbed conditions, showing a significant efficiency improvement over previous implementations.

Keywords: privacy-preservation, identity management, multi-signatures, Attribute-Based-Credentials, Zero-Knowledge

1. Introduction

Digital services have become an indispensable part of our ubiquitously networked society. Even more, with increasing digitization and the ever more frequently chosen “as-a-service” paradigm, the need for and use of online services continues to grow at a great pace. While key services related to authentication and authorization required in such a setting were often offered by Big Tech in the last decades, a trend reversal towards self-sovereignty has taken place in recent years, which puts the user in the center and gives them full control over their data.

The rise of the SSI (Self Sovereign Identity) paradigm is leading the research community to look into decentralized identity management systems where Identity Providers are no longer centralized, as this circumstance may lead to them becoming a potential point of failure and undertaking misuse of data. To avoid these problems, privacy-preserving Attribute Based Credentials (p-ABC) [1, 2] systems, which already offer

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unforgeability, minimal disclosure and unlinkability of user transactions, are being redesigned and reimplemented to become fully decentralized. In this regard, Pointcheval–Sanders Multi-Signatures (PS-MS) [3], unlike many other PS-based p-ABCs [4] allow a fully distributed issuance of user’s credentials employed in the p-ABC scheme, thereby minimizing the risk of curious IdPs and strengthening the overall security and privacy in Identity Management Systems. In a multi-signature based p-ABC scheme, every issuer computes its key shares and the global public key of the system is generated as an aggregation of the public key shares coming from the involved issuers.

PS-MS schemes have been successfully implemented in previous work [5] and thoroughly evaluated as part of the European projects OLYMPUS¹ and CyberSec4Europe². However, that solution, and in general the current state of the art distributed p-ABC (dp-ABC) schemes do not support yet several key advanced features desirable in a holistic fully decentralized and fully privacy-preserving identity management system. That is, while it is known within the cryptographic community how to realize certain features (e.g., range proofs) in p-ABC systems, existing implementations especially of dp-ABCs do not offer these extensions, making it hard (if not impossible) for practical systems to benefit from the scientific state-of-the-art. In particular, the following core features are missing in any such software framework:

- The protocols for the presentation phase, where users generate presentation tokens, achieve all-or-nothing unlinkability: either presentation tokens of the same user are fully unlinkable across and within a service provider, or they can be linked due to uniquely identifying disclosed attributes. What is not supported are pseudonyms which offer means for fine-granular and user-controlled linkability of presentation tokens.
- Current dp-ABC solutions implementations do not support the usage of proofs of range over the attributes aimed to demonstrate that a given attribute lies above or below a threshold value, or within a predefined interval. If such a predicate needs to be checked, currently the entire attribute value needs to be disclosed in cleartext to the service provider.
- In the few existing decentralized p-ABCs implementations, anonymity is unconditional. That is, they do not allow the inspection of the credential holder in case of misuse supported in some existing centralized schemes, which might permit entitled official entities (e.g., courts) to perform accountability and de-identification of users, e.g., in case of a cyber-crime.
- Finally, existing dp-ABCs frameworks do not support the revocation and invalidation of compromised credentials, beyond the basic mechanisms based on maintaining global epochs that degenerate the usability and scalability of the system.

To overcome the aforementioned shortcomings, this paper leverages previous work [5] providing a fully

¹<https://olympus-project.eu/>

²<https://cybersec4europe.eu/>

decentralized and modular privacy scheme that supports not only unforgeability, minimal disclosure, un-
45 linkability and distributed credential issuance across different IdPs, but also advanced features not applied
yet in a distributed p-ABC system based on PS-MS, extending the proving system to include pseudonyms,
revocation, inspection and range proofs. What is more, those extensions are enabled in a fully modular way
through the modification of the proving process to integrate commit-and-prove techniques, so implementing
further extensions like set-membership proofs [6] or binding of credentials to the biometrics of the credential
50 holder [7] will be simple.

In order to validate the feasibility and performance of the proposed scheme, it has been successfully
evaluated under different testbed conditions and it has been fully implemented, as open source, in a Java
library, plus a simplified C library achieving improved execution times. In addition, the proposed scheme
has been compared with the state of the art, outperforming the p-ABC system Idemix [8], the only work of
55 its kind that supports all the features and predicates considered in this paper in a modular way.

Summarizing, the contributions of this work are as follows:

- Formalized zero-knowledge presentation methods for dp-ABC based on Pointcheval-Sanders Multi-
Signatures that enable modular extensibility through commit-and-prove techniques. The extension is
a contribution of independent interest, as it is applicable to other PS-based p-ABC schemes that do
60 not modify the original verification formula.
- The modified presentation has been used to develop an open-source implementation of a dp-ABC
scheme that supports range proofs, inspection, pseudonyms and revocation, and can be easily extended.
- The system has been evaluated in different testbed conditions, proving its applicability in practical
scenarios, and significantly outperforms the Idemix system, the only current implementation of a p-
65 ABC that supports all predicates in this work and follows a similar modular approach.

1.1. Outline

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 3 summarizes notation and background used in
the paper. Section 4 formalizes the modular extension of the p-ABC presentation phase, while Section 5
introduces how it was applied to achieve four key extensions of ABCs and discusses practical design aspects
70 of such applications. Section 6 details evaluation results of the implementation. Lastly, the conclusions for
this work are recounted in Section 7.

2. Related work

Attribute-based credential systems. Attribute-based credential systems have first been envisioned by Chaum [1,
2] and have later been instantiated, e.g., IBM’s identity mixer (Idemix) [9, 10] or Microsoft’s UProve [11], and
75 in a large body of work proposing a variety of features and efficiency optimizations [12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18].

From works in ABCs, we remark [3], which introduced the dp-ABC scheme that serves as a basis of this work, and the scheme by Héban and Pointcheval [19], which also deals with multi-authority credentials based on aggregated signatures. However, in both cases the dp-ABC scheme does not support operations beyond selective disclosure of attributes, in contrast with the modular approach introduced here. Further, while the initial version of the former was implemented and evaluated in our previous work [5], the latter has not been implemented and evaluated.

Furthermore, a large variety of extensions functionalities has been suggested since their initial introduction, including, e.g., revocation [20, 21] to enable invalidation of a certificate through the issuer or the user, inspection [22, 23] to enable a trust party to identify the user computing a presentation token in case of abuse, range proofs [24, 25, 26, 27] to allow for proving predicates over attributes without revealing the precise value (e.g., age proofs), or pseudonyms [17] to give the user fine-granular flexibility under which conditions different presentations should be linkable or not.

Implementation efforts. Attribute-Based Credentials are seeing redoubled implementation efforts partly due to the rise of Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) models [28] and related initiatives like DIDs [29] or Verifiable Credentials [30]. This is the case of projects like Hyperledger’s Aries³ and the related cryptographic library Ursa⁴. The main focus in both is the use of BBS+ (c.f. [31]) as signatures for anonymous credentials, focusing exclusively basic protocols with only selective disclosure and e.g., no distributed issuance notions. The Ursa library does also include some support of PS signatures, but considers attribute predicates or distributed issuance out of scope. Another case is the implementation in [5], which focuses on the only existing multi-signature based ABC scheme. However, it only deals with selective disclosure of attributes, not supporting further predicate proofs over the credential.

There are some other implementations of p-ABCs based on different techniques. For instance, the implementation⁵ used in the H2020 project ABC4Trust [8] is designed for the Idemix library, and interoperable with UProve. The implementation supports various predicates in a modular way, including pseudonyms, revocation or inspection. However, it is no longer being maintained, and it does not consider the distributed issuance scenario. Furthermore, the system’s efficiency is lacking compared to ours, as shown in Section 6. Another system based on Idemix is IRMA authentication [32]. However, it focuses only on selective disclosure and revocation. Also, the system is tied to a specific application, and cannot be used as a re-usable p-ABC software⁶. For its part, the implementation⁷ of the anonymous credentials presented in [33] offers pseudonym and revocation functionality. However, in that work pseudonyms are generated by the issuer, and no other functionality is contemplated. Lastly, similar identity technologies are also receiving attention. For

³<https://www.hyperledger.org/use/aries>

⁴<https://www.hyperledger.org/use/ursa>

⁵<https://github.com/p2abcengine/p2abcengine>

⁶<https://github.com/privacybydesign>

⁷<https://github.com/hyperdivision/anonymous-credentials>

instance, Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA) [34], as implemented in ⁸ enables authentication of messages through signatures, while preserving privacy in a pseudonymous way (controlled linkability). However, it does not deal with the notion of attributes as p-ABCs do, and consequently, selective disclosure, range proofs
110 are out of its scope.

3. Preliminaries

In this section, we introduce the notation that will be used throughout the paper and describe the necessary background, mainly the p-ABC scheme we extend. We explain each topic at the level necessary to follow discussion in this paper, and refer to the original literature for further details, mainly [18, 3, 5]

115 3.1. Notation

We use \mathbf{v} to denote a vector (v_1, \dots, v_n) . We use $x \in_R X$ to represent that the element x has been sampled uniformly at random from a set X .

3.2. Pointcheval-Sanders (multi-)signatures

This work mainly focuses on Pointcheval-Sanders signatures [4, 18]. More concretely, our implementation
120 scenarios deal with the multi-signature variation introduced in [3]. This modification allows the combination of signatures from different signers so that the resulting signature is valid with respect to an aggregated version of their individual public keys.

Following the notation in [5], the interfaces of the scheme can be divided in three phases. In the *setup* phase, ***PS-MS.Setup*** establishes the public parameters (group instantiation, number of signers...); ***PS-MS.KG***
125 is used to generate key pairs; and ***PS-MS.KAggr*** to aggregate verification keys into a single public key. In the *issuance* phase, ***PS-MS.Sign*** is used to generate signatures, which can be combined with ***PS-MS.SAggr*** into a single one, and verified by executing ***PS-MS.Verf***. For more detailed descriptions on these methods we refer to [5].

Lastly, the presentation phase is the focus of this work. We again follow the same notation, expressing
130 it in a non-interactive way. The ***PS-MS.ZKProve*** method allows a holder of a signature to generate a zero-knowledge proof that selectively discloses some of the signed messages. The token can then be verified through ***PS-MS.ZKVerf***. For completeness sake, we include the full instantiations in the following.

Given a verification key avk , a signature σ , a set of messages $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{Z}_r^k$, a set of indexes of messages to be revealed R and hidden H (with $R \cup H = A = \{1, \dots, k\}$), a hash function H_2 , and a context ctx :

PS-MS.ZKProve($avk, \sigma, \mathbf{m}, R, ctx$) $\rightarrow tok$:

Take σ as (m', σ_1, σ_2) and compute $(\sigma'_1, \sigma'_2) = (\sigma_1^w, (\sigma_2 \sigma_1^z)^w)$ for $w, z \in_R \mathbb{Z}_r$. Then, compute the Schnorr's signature:

⁸<https://github.com/whotracksme/anonymous-credentials>

$\pi = \text{NIZK.Prove}\{(\mathbf{m}_H, z, m') : \text{PS-MS.Verf}(\text{avk}, \mathbf{m}, \sigma) = \text{True}\}(ctx)$

That is, choose random t_{m_j} $j \in H$, t_z and $t_{m'}$ and compute

$$t = \prod_{j \in H} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{t_j} e(\sigma_1', Y_{k+1})^{t_{m'}} e(\sigma_1', g_2)^{t_z}$$

135 Then, the challenge is $c = H_2(ctx, \text{avk}, \sigma_1', \sigma_2', t)$ and the signature is $\pi = (c, (v_{m_j})_{j \in H}, v_z, v_{m'})$, for $v_{m_j} = t_{m_j} - cm_j$, $v_z = t_z - cz$ and $v_{m'} = t_{m'} - cm'$. Return $\text{tok} = (\sigma_1', \sigma_2', \pi)$.

PS-MS.ZKVerf($\text{avk}, \text{tok}, \mathbf{m}_R, ctx$) \rightarrow **True/False**:

Take $\text{tok} = (\sigma_1', \sigma_2', \pi)$ with $\pi = (c, (v_{m_j})_{j \in H}, v_z, v_{m'})$. Then, verify that the signature of knowledge π is valid. That is, compute:

$$t' = \prod_{j \in H} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{v_{m_j}} e(\sigma_1', Y_{k+1})^{v_{m'}} e(\sigma_1', g_2)^{v_z} \cdot \prod_{j \in R} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{-cm_j} e(\sigma_1', X)^{-c} e(\sigma_2', g_2)^c$$

Calculate $c' = H_2(ctx, \text{avk}, \sigma_1', \sigma_2', t')$. Return true if $c = c'$ and false otherwise.

In previous works [18, 3], the scheme has been showed to fulfil existential unforgeability under chosen-message attacks (EUF-CMA) and the presentation phase being a zero-knowledge proof of knowledge, under
140 the assumptions (i) modified q-SDH assumption, which has been shown to hold on the generic bilinear group model (ii) the random oracle model .

3.3. Cryptographic Building blocks

In the paper, we will use some additional fundamental cryptographic building blocks. For self-contentedness and to introduce the notation used in the following, we give brief summaries of these primitives in the fol-
145 lowing; for in-depth discussions, we refer to the cited literature.

Commitment schemes. A commitment scheme allow one party to uniquely bind itself to a specific value, without revealing it to anybody else. However, at a later stage, the party can *open* the commitment by disclosing the committed value and some additional opening information.

A commitment scheme is *perfectly hiding*, if the commitment C does not contain any information about
150 the committed value m in an information-theoretic sense. Furthermore, it is *computationally binding*, if it is computationally infeasible to generate a commitment and two accepting openings to different messages. For formal definitions we refer to Pedersen [35].

In this work, we rely on Pedersen commitments [35]. Let therefore be G a group of prime order q , and g, h be random generators of G . A commitment to m is then computed as $C = g^m h^V$, where V is chosen
155 randomly within \mathbb{Z}_q . Given m and V , the validity of the opening can easily be checked by recomputing C .

This scheme is perfectly hiding and computationally binding under the discrete logarithm assumption in G . Additionally, it is possible to homomorphically modify the committed value through group multiplication, e.g. $C' = Cg^x = g^{x+m} h^V$.

Non-interactive zero-knowledge proofs. Intuitively, a non-interactive zero-knowledge proof of knowl-
 160 edge (NIZK) allows a prover to convince a verifier that it knows a secret piece of information without
 revealing anything beyond what is already revealed by the claim itself [36].

More formally, a NIZK is *zero-knowledge*, if, given access to a simulation trapdoor, proofs with a distri-
 bution indistinguishable from real proofs can also be generated only knowing the statement. On the other
 hand, *simulation-sound extractability* means that it is computationally hard to generate a valid proof for
 165 a statement and a context without knowing the corresponding witness, even after having seen arbitrarily
 many simulated proofs for statements chosen adaptively by the adversary [37].

For convenience, in following sections we use the notation introduced by Camenisch and Stadler [38],
 where a NIZK, bound to the context ctx , for values (α, β) that fulfil the right-hand side condition is denoted
 by:

$$pt \in_R \text{NIZK}[(\alpha, \beta) : g^\alpha h^\beta = y_1 \wedge \alpha \leq x](ctx)$$

All NIZKs used in this paper are based on so-called Σ -protocols [39, 40]. These are protocols consisting
 of three messages exchanged between the prover and the verifier: the prover first computes a *commitment*
 t , and receives back a *challenge* c randomly chosen by the verifier. The prover then computes a *response* s
 170 which is send back to the verifier, who decides whether to accept or to reject the transcript. Σ -protocols can
 now be made non-interactive by deploying the Fiat-Shamir heuristic [41, 42, 43], which essentially replaces
 the verifier’s random message by a random oracle called on t as well as relevant context information (e.g.,
 the description of the statement, the algebraic setting, etc.).

Public key encryption. Public key encryption allows any party, having access to the public key pk , to
 175 encrypt a message, while only the holder of the corresponding secret sk is able to recover the message
 encrypted in a ciphertext.

While different security notions for public key encryption exist, the notion required in this paper is
 indistinguishability under chosen plaintext attacks (IND-CPA). In a nutshell, this property requires that no
 adversary having access to pk can decide which message is contained in a ciphertext, even if the ciphertext
 180 encrypts one out of two messages previously chosen by the adversary. For a formal definition we refer to
 [44].

In this paper, we will use the ElGamal cryptosystem [45]. Let therefore again G be a group of prime
 order q , and g be a generator of G . Given a secret key sk and a public key $pk = g^{sk}$, an encryption $m \in G$
 is given by $c = (g^r, m \cdot pk^r)$ for r chosen randomly in \mathbb{Z}_q . To decrypt $c = (c_1, c_2)$, the holder of the secret
 185 key can compute m as $m = c_2 \cdot c_1^{-sk}$. The scheme satisfies IND-CPA under the decisional Diffie-Hellman
 assumption.

Pseudonym systems. Scope-exclusive pseudonym systems allow a user holding secret key sk to derive a
 string which uniquely identifies them within a given context, but are fully unlinkable across contexts. This in

particular allows users to be known to different parties (e.g., service providers) under different pseudonyms, while still allowing those to re-identify a returning user.

Let again G be a group of prime order q , and let $Hash$ be a cryptographic hash function mapping to elements of G . Given a scope ctx , a pseudonym can then be computed as $Hash(ctx)^{sk}$. It can be shown that this construction is secure (i.e., collision-resistant and unlinkable) under the decisional Diffie-Hellman assumption [17].

4. Enabling modular extensions for PS based dp-ABC

In this section, we introduce and formalize the modified presentation phase of the p-ABC scheme based on Pointcheval-Sander Multi-Signatures (PS-MS) that is the basis for the modular extensibility of the system through commit-and-prove techniques.

With this approach, we improve the scenario in [5], summarized in Figure 1a, which only allowed selective disclosure of dp-ABCs. Now, it is possible to fine-granularly disclose information within the credential through statements over the attribute values, for instance showing numeric attributes are above or below a threshold. Additionally, other desirable security features, like controlled linkability or inspection and revocation, may be included. These additions require extra entities and flows in the system. For instance, Figure 1b shows the system resulting from the application of the features implemented in this work, which will be thoroughly discussed in Section 5.

Figure 1: Scenario and flows supported by new dp-ABC functionality (b), in contrast to previous solution [5] (a).

4.1. The modified protocol

The main idea behind the modified protocol is adding the possibility of linking a (Pedersen) commitment of an attribute to a signature over, among others, said attribute. Thus, it becomes possible to take advantage of commit-and-prove schemes to extend the functionality of the p-ABC system in a modular way, an idea gaining traction in current literature, e.g. [6].

On a high level, consider the scenario where one wants to prove knowledge of a valid credential on attributes satisfying a certain relation \mathcal{R} , i.e., where the following proof π needs to be computed:

$$\pi = \text{NIZK.Prove} \{(attrs_H, \sigma, x) : PS - MS.Verf((attrs_H, attrs_R), \sigma) = 1 \wedge (x, a_i) \in \mathcal{R}\}$$

for some $a_i \in attrs_H$, where x is a witness for a_i with respect to \mathcal{R} . Here $attrs_H$ denote the attributes that remain *hidden* during the presentation, while $attrs_R$ denotes the *revealed* attributes.

In order to achieve modularity, this proof goal is now split into two goals which are bound by a linking commitment, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi' &= \text{NIZK.Prove} \{(attrs_H, \sigma, o) : PS - MS.Verf((attr_H, attr_R), \sigma) = 1 \wedge V = Y_i^{a_i} X^o\}, \text{ and} \\ \pi'' &= \text{NIZK.Prove} \{(a_i, x, o) : V = Y_i^{a_i} X^o \wedge (x, a_i) \in \mathcal{R}\} \end{aligned}$$

See also Figure 2 for a graphical representation of the approach.

Figure 2: Schematic view of the modular extension of showings

The validity of this decomposition is easy to verify: firstly, zero-knowledge is maintained, as both proofs
 215 are zero-knowledge, and the used commitment scheme is perfectly hiding. Secondly, soundness is maintained, as forging a proof would either require to forge a proof π' or π'' , which would break the soundness of the underlying proof system, or would require to open the commitment V to different values, which is intractable under the discrete logarithm assumption. Formal details on this approach can be found, e.g., in [6].

Extending PS-MS proofs. In the following we now describe in more details the modified schemes for
 220 proving knowledge of a PS multi-signature.

We use the notation from Section 3 for the PS-MS scheme. Now, the set of indexes for the attributes (A) will be divided in revealed (R), hidden (H) and involved in commit-and-prove scheme (P), so $A = R \cup H \cup P$ with R, H, P disjoint. For each attribute m_p , $p \in P$, we have a Pedersen commitment $V_p = h_p^{\gamma} g^{m_p}$, where γ_p is a random blinding factor chosen by the holder. We denote the set of blinding factors as γ_P , and the
 225 set of commitments as V_P .

Given the verification key $vk = (X, Y_1, \dots, Y_{k+1}) \in G_2^{*k+2}$, we set X and Y_p as the commitment base elements h and g for each attribute m_p . With this choice, we achieve a straightforward and efficient integration of the linkage of an attribute commitment into the the scheme's signature verification formulas as used in the presentation phase. What is more, this removes the need of additional trusted setup for the commitment

230 parameters, as they come form public information of the scheme that must be available to prover and verifier anyway.

Note that this setup may seem to introduce possible attack vectors for malicious or compromised issuers: if an attacker knows discrete logarithms of the basis, Pedersen commitments are no longer binding. In fact, such party it can collude with another one to provide them non-binding commitments without revealing the
 235 secret logarithms it knows. Thus, the soundness of the solution would be jeopardized. However, this *does not change* the threat model for our solution in any practical scenario. What is more, in our specific scenario, with distributed issuance, the likelihood of such an occurrence is reduced. Indeed:

- In the distributed setting of PS-MS, no one controls a secret key for the public key of the whole set of issuers, unless they all collude or are compromised.
- 240 • Even in the latter case (or if there is a single issuer), an attacker with control of the key would not need to break (or help break) the binding property of the commitment scheme to trick a verifier. Instead, it can simply generate for itself (or a user) a valid credential that fulfils the required statement. Thus, it gains no advantage through this new attack vector. In summary, in the only scenarios where the binding property of the commitment scheme is broken because of this choice, there are simpler, and
 245 unavoidable, attacks that achieve the same purpose.

The full definition of the modified presentation methods follows:

PS-MS.ZKProveMod($avk, \sigma, \mathbf{m}, R, P, \gamma_P, msg$) $\rightarrow tok$:

Take σ as (m', σ_1, σ_2) and compute $(\sigma'_1, \sigma'_2) = (\sigma_1^w, (\sigma_2 \sigma_1^z)^w)$ for $w, z \in_R \mathbb{Z}_r$, and $V_j = X^{\gamma_j} Y_p^{m_j}$ $j \in P$.

Then, compute the modified Schnorr's signature:

$$\pi = NIZK.Prove\{(\mathbf{m}_H, z, \mathbf{m}_P, \gamma_P, \sigma) : PS - MS.Verf(avk, \mathbf{m}, \sigma) = True\}^9, V_P = X^{\gamma_j} Y_j^{m_j}, j \in P\}(msg)$$

That is, choose random t_{m_j} $j \in H$, t_z, t_{γ_j} $j \in P$ and $t_{m'}$ and compute

$$t = \prod_{j \in H \cup P} e(\sigma'_1, Y_j)^{t_{m_j}} e(\sigma'_1, Y_{k+1})^{t_{m'}} e(\sigma'_1, g_2)^{t_z} \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma'_1, X)^{t_{\gamma_j}}$$

Then, the challenge is $c = H_2(msg, avk, \sigma'_1, \sigma'_2, V_P, t)$ and the signature is

$$\pi = (c, (v_{m_j})_{j \in H \cup P}, v_z, (v_{\gamma_j})_{j \in P}, v_{m'}), \text{ for } v_{m_j} = t_{m_j} - cm_j \text{ } j \in H, v_{m_j} = t_{m_j} - 2cm_j \text{ } j \in P, v_z = t_z - cz, v_{m'} = t_{m'} - cm' \text{ and } v_{\gamma_j} = t_{\gamma_j} - c\gamma_j \text{ } j \in P.$$

250 Return $tok = (\sigma'_1, \sigma'_2, \pi)$.

PS-MS.ZKVerfMod($avk, tok, \mathbf{m}_R, V_P, msg$) $\rightarrow \text{True/False}$:

Take $tok = (\sigma'_1, \sigma'_2, \pi)$ with $\pi = (c, (v_{m_j})_{j \in H}, v_z, v_{\gamma_j}, v_{m'})$.

⁹In fact, we do not directly use Verification with σ , but the relationship using σ' . However, translating the relationship in terms of σ and σ' (and vice-versa) is simple as shown in the original proposal [4]

Then, verify that the signature of knowledge π is valid. That is, compute:

$$t' = \prod_{j \in H \cup P} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{v_{mj}} e(\sigma_1', Y_{k+1})^{v_{m'}} e(\sigma_1', g_2)^{v_z} \cdot \prod_{j \in R} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{-cm_j} \cdot e(\sigma_1', X)^{-c} e(\sigma_2', g_2)^c \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', V_j)^c \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', X)^{v_{rj}}$$

Calculate $c' = H_2(msg, avk, \sigma_1', \sigma_2', V_P, t')$. Return true if $c = c'$ and false otherwise.

4.2. Security analysis

In this paper, we extend the scheme described in [3, 5] modularly by modifying the algorithms used in the presentation phase. As a design goal, we aimed at not modifying the underlying security models and definitions. The results described in this paper rely on the same assumptions as in the original papers. Namely, the security is proven under the random oracle and a variant of the q-SDH assumption, which was shown to hold on the generic bilinear group model. The security properties achieved are also the same, existential unforgeability under chosen message attacks and non-interactive zero knowledge for the showing phase.

In the following we show that the only modified part, the presentation phase, which still fulfils the same security property as in the original [5], namely that it is a non-interactive zero-knowledge proof of knowledge.

Proposition 1. *The algorithms $PS-MS.ZKProveMod$ and $PS-MS.ZKVerfMod$ constitute a non-interactive zero-knowledge proof of knowledge.*

Proof. Instead of considering the non-interactive notation of the methods as described previously, in the proof we will work with an interactive version of the protocol run between a Prover (**P**) and Verifier (**V**). We show that the interactive protocol is a zero-knowledge proof of knowledge (specifically, a Σ -protocol) and public coin. We then finalize the proof by remarking that the non-interactive version is a signature of knowledge that can be achieved by applying the Fiat-Shamir heuristic and adding a message to the hash computation.

The new protocol constructions consist on a *modification* of the Schnorr protocol used in the original scheme [3]. Thus, if we show that the modified Schnorr protocol is a zero-knowledge proof of knowledge, the ideas shown in [4] to prove that the protocol as a whole is a zero-knowledge proof of knowledge are still valid. In the following paragraph, we summarize those ideas and refer to the original for full details.

Namely, $\sigma' = (\sigma_1', \sigma_2') = (\sigma_1^w, (\sigma_2 \sigma_1^z)^w)$ is taken into account for completeness verification.

Regarding soundness, once z is extracted, it is possible to compute $(\sigma'' = (\sigma_1', \sigma_2' \sigma_1^{-z}))$, which is a valid signature (same computations as in original paper are valid).

Additionally, σ' can be simulated by generating two random elements, as z, w are chosen randomly and thus the distribution in the original computation is also uniformly random.

From the previous discussion, we can now focus on the modified Schnorr protocol, assuming that **V** learns σ_1', σ_2' as public values. The commitment values, V_P , are in fact also public, as they are used in

the protocols for extended predicates. In any case, we can follow the same approach and simulate them by generating random elements as their distribution will be indistinguishable from the uniform (in other words, Pedersen commitments are perfect hiding). We also include Schnorr-style commitment-response pairs to the challenge c in the proof, so the witnesses of the Pedersen commitments can be retrieved by the extractor.

285 Both aspects are shown in the in the soundness and zero-knowledge arguments presented below.

The interactive protocol is as follows:

1. \mathbf{P} sends V_P and t to \mathbf{V} .
2. \mathbf{V} chooses $c \in_R \mathbb{Z}_r$ and sends it to \mathbf{P}
3. \mathbf{P} computes $(v_{m_j})_{j \in H}, v_z, v_\gamma, v_{m'}$ and sends them to \mathbf{V}
- 290 4. \mathbf{V} uses them to compute t' and checks $t' = t$.

Where the formulas for computing t and t' are the same as depicted in the method definitions in this section. We will show that this protocol is an honest-verifier zero-knowledge proof of knowledge. For this, we follow the common approach in Σ protocols, proving completeness, *special* soundness through a witness extractor, and *honest-verifier* zero-knowledge through a simulator.

Completeness

We will work with the added (or modified) terms in the formulas to prove that $t = t'$ holds (verifier accepts) when \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{V} follow the protocol:

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', V_j)^c &= \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', X^{\gamma_j} Y_j^{m_j})^c = \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', X)^{c \gamma_j} \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{c m_j} \\ \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{v_{m_j}} &= \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{t_{m_j} - 2c m_j} \\ e(\sigma_1', X)^{v_{\gamma_j}} &= e(\sigma_1', X)^{t_{\gamma_j} - c \gamma_j} \end{aligned}$$

295 Thus, we can rewrite t' (with $v'_{m_j} = t_{m_j} - c m_j$ $j \in P$) as:

$$\begin{aligned} t' &= \prod_{j \in H} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{v_{m_j}} \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{v'_{m_j}} e(\sigma_1', Y_{k+1})^{v_{m'}} e(\sigma_1', g_2)^{v_z} \cdot \prod_{j \in R} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{-c m_j} \\ &\quad \cdot e(\sigma_2', g_2)^c e(\sigma_1', X)^{-c} \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', X)^{t_{\gamma_j}} \end{aligned}$$

We note that the expression is equivalent to one that appears in the original presentation methods with $H \cup P$ being hidden attributes, except for the last term $\prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', X)^{t_{\gamma_j}}$. Thus, we can assure that $t' = t'' \cdot \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', X)^{t_{\gamma_j}}$, where

$$t'' = \prod_{j \in H \cup P} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{t_{m_j}} e(\sigma_1', Y_{k+1})^{t_{m'}} e(\sigma_1', g_2)^{t_z}$$

Immediately follows that $t' = t$, finishing the proof.

(Special) Soundness

As the v values are computed in the same way as in Σ protocols and there is a value for each hidden element ($m_j, j \in H \cup P, \gamma_j, j \in P, z, m'$), we can follow the same approach to get an extractor that gets the witnesses from two accepting conversations equal up to the point where the verifier sends a challenge (i.e., the extractor interacts with prover and once it receives a response for challenge c , it rewinds and sends another challenge c'). For example, $\gamma_j = (v_{\gamma_j} - v'_{\gamma_j})(c' - c)^{-1}$, or $m_j = (v_{m_j} - v'_{m_j})(2c' - 2c)^{-1}$ for $j \in P$.

(Honest-verifier) Zero-Knowledge

We assume the verifier follows the protocol honestly, i.e., chooses c randomly and independently of the input received in the first step. A simulator S can generate a valid transcript:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P &\rightarrow V : V_P, t \\
 V &\rightarrow P : c \\
 P &\rightarrow V : \{v_j\}
 \end{aligned}$$

By choosing uniformly random $V_P, \{v_j\}$ from \mathbb{Z}_r^* and computing t with the same formula that will be used by the verifier. As before, the simulator is given the ability to rewind after the verifier sends the challenge, so it knows c because of the honest-verifier setting.¹⁰ That is, it computes:

$$\begin{aligned}
 t = & \prod_{j \in H \cup P} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{v_{m_j}} e(\sigma_1', Y_{k+1})^{v_{m'}} e(\sigma_1', g_2)^{v_z} \cdot \prod_{j \in R} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{-cm_j} \\
 & \cdot e(\sigma_1', X)^{-c} e(\sigma_2', g_2)^c \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', V_j)^c \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', X)^{v_{\gamma_j}}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this way, the resulting distributions are indistinguishable and a third party can verify the transcript as valid.

Lastly, the protocol is public-coin (i.e., the random choices, in this case choosing the challenge c , made by the verifier are made public), so it can be transformed into a non-interactive proof in the random oracle model using the Fiat-Shamir heuristic and, specifically, a signature of knowledge including the message m in the computation [43]. □

4.3. Implementation

The implementation has followed the modular approach presented in [5], and is fully integrated in the previous identity management codebase. That is, each of the applications described in the following section has been implemented in Java as a standalone functionality using the interfaces for modular arithmetic and elliptic curve functionality previously defined in the framework. In addition, the methods introduced in this section have also been implemented, so that zero-knowledge proofs that link commitments to the credential attributes are enabled. Lastly, we implemented logic so that both client and verifier can automatically handle

¹⁰An alternative view is that the simulator can generate the whole transcript by (uniformly) randomly choosing c and performing the same steps, generating a transcript with the same distribution as a real transcript.

the new predicates. Specifically, they will compute/verify the specific proofs for each attribute according to the implemented module, and link the commitment to the credential through the new methods.

5. Applications

In this section, we review the functionalities that have been integrated with the scheme through the modified presentation protocol. Of course, these are not a comprehensive list of functionalities that can result from the application of the commit-and-prove ideas, as this paradigm offers a great deal of flexibility to scheme construction as remarked in [46]. Our work has focused on the most commonly required extended functionalities of p-ABC schemes. The application of these protocols depends on the specific use case needs, and any combination of them can be used without modifying the underlying scheme or implementation.

A summary on the impact of the new applications in the dp-ABC scenario was shown in Figure 1. In the new setting it is now possible to show that a numeric attribute, such as a date, is above or below a threshold, enabling further granularity for presentations. Additionally, it is possible to derive scope-exclusive pseudonyms, that can be applied for controlled linkability within a scope. Lastly, two security features that can be applied, e.g., when a credential is misused, are enabled: revocation and inspection. Both require the participation of a new formal entity in the system: the authority that governs the process. The rest of the section gives a detailed overview on these applications, how they are implemented in our approach and practical aspects related to their deployment.

5.1. Range proofs

Range proofs enhance the binary privacy options of credential systems – an attribute is either disclosed or not – by a more fine-granular feature: namely, the allow one to prove that an attribute value lies above or below a threshold value, or within a predefined interval, without disclosing the actual attribute value.

Range proofs are arguably among the most useful and most crucial extensions of basic attribute-based credential systems, enabling an almost overwhelming number of applications. For instance, range proofs contribute to data minimization when requiring to prove that a user is above (or below) a certain age, e.g., to obtain a discount or special rate. Also, range proofs can be used to encode expiration dates and prove upon presentation that the credential has not yet been expired, without leaking additional metadata through disclosure of the expiration date. While generic approaches for proving set membership, e.g., based on accumulators [47] could be used for proving that a witness lies in some interval, more optimized solutions depending on the concrete algebraic setting, the size of the range, or the computational resources available at prover and verifier, respectively, a variety of options for range proofs have been described in the literature, including, e.g., bit-decomposition [26], schemes based on fuzzy range proofs [27], techniques based on Lagrange’s four-square theorem [25], or Bulletproofs [24].

Also, beyond the immediate context of ABCs, zero-knowledge range proofs are often used as building blocks in higher-level applications, e.g., related to know your customer (KYC) requirements in the financial

sector [48], electronic auctions [49], electronic voting [50], or confidential transactions on blockchains [51], cf. also Morais et al. [52] for a survey on applications.

For our implementation, we opted for Bulletproofs introduced by Bunz et al [24], providing concise proofs logarithmic in the bit-length of the range as well as high efficiency on prover and especially verifier sides. However, there is a small caveat for Bulletproofs: because of the recursive proof strategy, they only support ranges of the form $[0, 2^{2^n} - 1]$ out of the box. Fortunately, this issue can be easily circumvented by working with *offsets* to prove values for arbitrary ranges, cf. Camenisch et al. [53].

We would like to stress that in general their approach requires two proofs to avoid possible forgeries through modular arithmetic overflows. However, in our scenario, where the attribute that is being proven is linked to a valid credential certified by an issuer, these overflows can be ruled out, so only one protocol run will be needed for one-sided range proofs. Note that this does not require any additional trust assumption into the issuer, as the relying party anyways needs to fully trust the issuer in the sense that it will not certify incorrect information.

The integration of the range proof with the presentation proof is now achieved as follows. As part of *ZkProveMod*, the prover computes $V = Y_i^{a_i} X^o$ as a bridging commitment for the attribute a_i for which the relation is to be proven. Leveraging the techniques mentioned before, the prover then computes:

$$\pi = NIZK.Prove\{(a'_i, o) : V' = Y_i^{a'_i} X^o \wedge a'_i \in [0, 2^n - 1]\},$$

where both the verifier and the prover locally compute $V' = V \cdot Y_i^{offset}$ and the verifier uses the witness $a'_i = a_i + offset$, see also Figure 3 for a schematic summary.

Figure 3: **Range protocol implementation** Schematic summary of the integration of a range proof over attribute x .

For range proofs to be possible, the encoding of attributes needs to be order-preserving, in particular ruling out common techniques like hashing. Integer attributes can be mapped into the attribute space \mathbb{Z}_r by simple interval shifts, i.e., $[a, b]$ can be shifted to $[0, b - a]$, thereby encoding a value x as $x - a$. Similarly, timestamps can be considered as integers in the usual way (number of seconds, days, ... from a reference point), and then encoded in the same way.

Also, as will be shown in Section 6, range proofs are much more expensive than other operations tackled in this paper. While Bulletproofs are among the most widespread approaches in current solutions because of their efficiency, specifically in the verification step, in some cases other approaches—like a straightforward proof based on bit decomposition, which is cheaper for the prover at the cost of significantly more expen-

sive verification—might be better suited for a specific use-case, depending on the size of the intervals, the
 375 computational resources available at prover and verifier, or communication costs.

5.2. Inspection

In their vanilla form, p-ABCs provide full anonymity as long as users do not reveal identifying attributes. That is, no entity is able to infer any information about the user apart from what the user actively agrees to disclose upon a showing. However, such high anonymity guarantees hamper the security of the ecosystem
 380 in some scenarios through unaccountability in case of malicious use. For instance, when abusing anonymity for hate speech in online discussion forums, it may be desirable to have some means to re-identify the user and hold them accountable for their actions.

Therefore, another common feature of p-ABC systems is inspection [22, 23]. Inspection offers a trade-off between the anonymity of presentations and accountability. Namely, it allows a dedicated trusted entity (the
 385 *inspector*) agreed upon by the user and the verifier before presenting a credential, to recover information about the credential holder from a transcript of a presentation showing, e.g., some specific attributes of the user or a precise identifier. Inspection now serves as a compromise where anonymity remains in most cases, but can be revoked when justified. In practice, to achieve full transparency, the presentation policy would not only need to specify the inspector, but also the precise conditions under which the inspector may be
 390 called by the verifier to avoid abuse of this de-identification functionality.

In the example mentioned above, the inspector could, e.g., be given by a judge who only re-identifies an online user in case of criminally relevant hate postings. As another example, in the case of anonymous online contracts, an arbitration board could de-anonymize a party in case of a breach of agreement.

Technically, inspection is usually achieved by encrypting some identifying attribute under the public key
 395 of the inspector. The presentation is then modified such that it additionally proves in zero-knowledge that the encrypted attribute is consistent with the one certified in the credential.

Following the generic construction outlined in Section 4, inspection is now achieved as outlined in Figure 4. In a first step, as part of *ZkProveMod*, the verifier prover a bridging commitment V to the agreed identifying attribute id , i.e., $V = Y_{id}^{id} X^o$. In addition, the prover computes an ElGamal encryption $E = (b^{rand}, b^{id} k^{rand})$ of the identifying attribute, using the inspector’s public key (b, k) . Finally, using a Schnorr-like protocol and the Fiat-Shamir heuristic, the prover computes a NIZK proving that E and V are consistent, i.e., it computes

$$\pi = NIZK.Prove\{(id, rand, o) : V = Y_{id}^{id} X^o \wedge E_1 = b^{rand} \wedge E_2 = b^{id} k^{rand}\}.$$

The construction above also shows some of the benefits of our generic approach using linking commitments instead of directly broadening the presentation proof itself. Namely, for inspection it is not required to forward the entire presentation proof to the inspector, but only the additional zero-knowledge proof.
 400 Consequently, the inspector does not need to learn full details about, e.g., the disclosed attributes, but only learns the minimum information required for re-identifying the user. This is fully in line with recent work on group signatures, aiming for a similar goal, e.g., [54].

Figure 4: **Inspection protocol implementation** Schematic summary of the integration of inspection

In the current implementation we assume that only legit presentation tokens are handed to the inspector, which may be enforced by the processes checking whether or not such a token may actually be de-anonymized. However, formally in this case we only achieve a CPA-style of anonymity, i.e., in case that arbitrary tokens may be handed to the inspector, it formally would then act as a decryption oracle. A straightforward way to overcome this issue would be to add a second ElGamal encryption E' of id under a different key, equally owned by the inspector, and extend the proof to also show consistency with this second encryption. The resulting construction would then offer CCA-security according to Naor and Yung [44]. As can also be concluded from Section 6, the performance impact of this additional construction would be marginal, and the changes to our implementation would also be highly limited.

Finally, we want to mention that a property related to inspection is non-frameability, which means that even a malicious issuer will not be able to generate a presentation that points to a specific user. This is typically achieved by having a user-chosen attribute as part of the credential, to which the user knows an additional backdoor (e.g., a preimage) which is not revealed upon issuance. Upon presentation, the user now not only proves possession of the credential, but also knowledge of this secret information. However, we do not consider such a construction necessary in our scenario, as generating a credential pointing to a specific user would require all distributed issuers to collude, and thus a single point of attack is excluded, with the advantage of avoiding the associated performance impact upon presentation.

5.3. Pseudonyms

The attribute-based credentials implemented in [5] offer a very high level of anonymity. Namely, as long as no identifying attributes are being disclosed, multiple actions of the same user are fully unlinkable. However, in turn this also implies some kind of all-or-nothing linkability: either an action is fully unlinkable, or it can be linked to all other showings disclosing the same identifying attribute.

A possible way out is the use of so-called scope-exclusive pseudonyms, see, e.g., Camenisch et al. [17]. Such schemes allow a user to deterministically derive pseudonyms for specific scopes; now, by the determinism, showings for the same scope can be linked, while showings for different scopes are computationally unlinkable under standard complexity assumptions.

As a result, the user obtains fine-granular control regarding their linkability. For instance, for state-keeping service providers, users may choose the same pseudonym for every authentication; doing so, they will be able to access their state (e.g., preferences for a recommender system), while being unlinkable across

service providers. Even more, users could use different pseudonyms for different accounts at the same service provider (e.g., one per family member, or to separate work and private life), without the provider being able to link the different accounts. On the other hand, service providers may be interested in using such pseudonym systems too, as they could offer, e.g., a compromise between anonymity and prevention of account-sharing. For instance, service providers may request pseudonyms for a time-dependent scope with a certain granularity (e.g., one hour or day). Now, authentication sessions of the same user would be linkable within this timeframe, but unlinkable over larger time scales. This would give honest users high anonymity guarantees, while enabling the service provider to detect massive account sharing, in which case the anonymity of the account could be revoked, e.g., in combination with the techniques described in Section 5.2.

Technically, pseudonyms are usually achieved by including a secret attribute upon issuance which is never revealed. Instead, the pseudonym is derived from this specific attribute as well as the public scope agreed upon between the prover and the verifier. The prover then proves that the very same undisclosed attribute that has been signed by the issuer has also been used to derive the pseudonym.

Leveraging the generic construction from Section 4, the concrete construction for scope-exclusive pseudonyms is now depicted in Figure 5. First, $ZkProveMod$ generates a bridging commitment $V = Y_{id}^{id} X^o$, where id is the hidden attribute, and o is a random element. Following Camenisch et al. [17], the pseudonym is computed as $P = Hash(scope)^{id}$, where $Hash : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow G$ is a cryptographic hash function modelled as a random oracle. The prover then computes a NIZK proving that V and P are consistent, i.e., it generates

$$\pi = NIZK.Prove\{(id, o) : V = Y_{id}^{id} X^o \wedge P = Hash(scope)^{id}\}.$$

Figure 5: **Pseudonym protocol implementation** Schematic summary of the integration of scope pseudonyms

When used in combination with inspection, in order to minimize the overhead of the different add-ons, the same attribute id may actually be used for inspection and the pseudonym, in which case also the same bridging commitment can be used to reduce the computational overhead.

From a practical point of view, we also want to mention that pseudonyms give the user the possibility to prove or disprove their authorship of a showing without involving the inspector, similar to, e.g., Krenn et al. [54]. Despite the benefits, this may also introduce a level of coercability in certain applications, such that the decision whether or not to use pseudonyms may require a prior impact assessment. Also, to avoid that users become overly linkable, the selection of scopes, e.g., in the account sharing use case above, needs to be carefully evaluated, and the policies need to be communicated to the user highly transparently. Although the

455 full definition of a strategy for defining scopes is beyond the purpose of this paper, we note that an approach using verifiable data registries can cover both the needs for trustworthy distribution of key material and service provider policies (including scopes), whose behaviour can then be checked by all participants, as proposed by Moreno et al. [55].

5.4. Revocation

460 While the high anonymity guarantees in attribute-credential systems may be highly desirable from a user’s point of view, they also come with the risk of abuse. As explained above, this may be countered by the use of pseudonyms and inspection, yet ultimately it is also required to invalidate a credential to avoid further misuse. Similarly, the need for revocation may occur, e.g., when a device of the legitimate credential owner gets compromised or lost, or if relevant attributes change, e.g., a name in the course of a marriage.

465 The basic system presented by García-Rodríguez et al. [5] addresses this issue by offering a very coarse-grained solution: in a nutshell, credentials are equipped with an epoch encoded as a special attribute, which is disclosed at every showing such that the verifier can easily check the validity. Unfortunately, this approach requires a system-wide counter for the epoch, and does not allow for different requirements by different relying parties, yet of course different epoch-counters for different types of credentials (e.g., service subscriptions or 470 driving licenses) are conceivable. Also, this approach does not allow for revocation of individual credentials within one epoch, and requires all participants to obtain new credentials for the next epoch. Finally, while appropriate for services where credentials are valid, e.g., for a calendar month, their solution does not easily support scenarios where, e.g., the credential is valid for four weeks from the date of issuance.

For our extension, we took an *allow-list* approach. That is, on the one hand, each credential contains a 475 secret attribute rh selected during issuance and kept confidential upon presentation. On the other hand, a dedicated revocation authority (which may, but does not need to, coincide with the issuer) regularly publishes the currently valid revocation handles. Upon presentation, the prover shows that the value rh contained in their credential is also contained in the revocation authority’s allow-list.

Technically, we opted for a signature-based allow-list. That is, the revocation authority maintains a public registry of signed $(epoch, rh)$ pairs for all currently valid revocation handles. Here, in contrast to before, $epoch$ is a counter which is adjusted as needed, e.g., every time a credential is invalidated. This is realistic in scenarios where revocation is a very rare event, e.g., for academic degrees that only need to be revoked upon plagiarism [56]. To avoid losing unlinkability, we again rely on Pointcheval-Sanders signatures, so that a credential showing will involve two runs of the $ZkProveMod$ method, one for the identity credential and another one for the revocation credential, obtaining two bridging commitments V (from the main credential) and V' (from the revocation credential). Finally, the prover simply shows that V and V' contain the same value rh , i.e., they compute

$$\pi = NIZK.Prove\{rh, o, r : V = Y_{rh}^{rh} X^o \wedge V' = Y_{rh}'^{rh} X'^r\}.$$

Figure 6: **Revocation protocol implementation** Schematic summary of the integration of revocation.

In the literature, a variety of different approaches for revocation has been proposed, e.g., based on deny-
 480 lists [57] or using cryptographic accumulators [58, 59]. Let us thus briefly discuss some design choices of our
 revocation mechanism.

Firstly, using a signature-based allow-list approach means that all users need to fetch new revocation
 credentials every time a user is revoked in the system. However, in practice, the revocation authority may
 publish the signatures on a public registry, and users simply download their credentials in an ad-hoc manner
 485 when required for authentication, i.e., there is no need for any real-time interaction with the revocation
 authority or secret communication channels per user. While the overhead for the revocation authority is
 thus linear in the number of users, the effort per user is constant, and intermediary updates may safely be
 skipped by a user after longer periods of inactivity. This is in contrast to allow-lists based on cryptographic
 accumulators, which would either require communication channels from the authority to the user to transfer
 490 the new witness, or cause higher computational costs on the user’s side (e.g., in case that updates have been
 missed). Furthermore, verifiers for non-critical services may decide to accept revocation credentials not older
 than a threshold of epochs ago, such that the number of updates is further reduced.

Secondly, we believe that with the combination of static epochs in the original implementation, the
 possibility to encode expiration dates using the techniques from Section 5.1, and the presented allow-list
 495 approach, a maximum level of flexibility is offered to system developers.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that in fact the approach also allows for verifier-local revocation. That is,
 verifiers may act as revocation authorities on their own right by maintaining their own allow-lists, and decide
 to no longer accept certain users after misbehavior, without the need to invalidate an underlying credential,
 e.g., issued by a public authority.

500 6. Performance Evaluation

This section presents the evaluation of the extended implementation. We have studied the time needed
 to perform the different functionalities described in Section 5, including various size parameters for range
 proofs covering not only the most common cases but also specialized ones with high-precision demands.
 Additionally, we compare the results with the Identity Mixer system, as it is the main mature system (used
 505 in European projects like ARIES [60]) that fully implements various p-ABC functionalities in a modular way,

similarly to this work. Additionally, we show further feasibility results of our approach, with experiments on a mobile phone, as well as using a C implementation of the cryptographic operations for better performance. See Table A.2 in Appendix A for a summary of the results of all the experiments.

Testbed. The experiments have been carried out through the direct measurement of executions in the Java implementation, an extended and improved version of the one introduced in [5]. The results discussed in this section (except for the specific tests for a mobile phone, c.f. 6.3) correspond to experiments carried out in a laptop with an Intel Core i7-9750H CPU at 2.60 GHz and 16GB of RAM. The pairing-friendly curve used for the implementation was *BLS12-461*, which is estimated to provide more than 134 bits of security [61]. We note that when we report the number of attributes used in an experiment, it does not include the mandatory *epoch* attribute, which must be revealed when doing any presentation. Each experiment is repeated 30 times and the mean and standard deviation are reported (with 30 extra warm-up iterations at the start of an execution whose times are discarded).

6.1. Analysis of the extension and applications

Here, we show the results for both the proving and verifying phases of the showing process. Note that we measure the execution time for the complete method, which not only includes the cryptographic operations (in any case, the heaviest part of the computation by far), but also policy parsing, (de-)serialization of results. . . We measure timings for a *basic reveal policy* (BRP) with 4 hidden attributes as a basis for reference. Then, we take measurements for each of the applications in Section 5, by adding one such predicate (and the corresponding attribute to the credential) to the presentation policy.

In the range predicate case, we take measurements for various parameter values. The cost of range proofs depends on the size—i.e., number of bits needed to represent the encoded value—of the range’s boundaries. In particular, because of the nature of Bulletproofs (and the inner-product argument they are based on), the complexity depends on whether the values involved in the proof fit in 2^n bits. We took measurements for $n = 4, 5, 6$, because they cover practical use cases:

- 16 bits (2^4) are enough for representing integer attributes in many use cases, e.g. percentages (disability rate), scores. . . Additionally, date values are represented as number of time units (seconds, days. . .) since a reference point (e.g., Unix epoch). Most commonly, the granularity applied is *days*. In that scenario, periods of 180 years can be represented using 16 bits, which will be enough most of the time. One such case is identity documents, like electronic passports.
- 32 bits (2^5) encoding serves for most other use cases that involve integers, e.g. salaries or capital gains. Even for dates with *seconds* granularity, periods of more than 130 years are covered.
- 64 bits (2^6) or more will not be necessary in most use cases, but it might be useful when working with high precision data (e.g., for representing decimal numbers with high fidelity).

Figure 7 shows a comparison between credential showings for the base policy and the inspection, pseudonym, and revocation application cases. In all cases, the methods take significantly less than 100 milliseconds, which shows the practicality of the proposed instantiation. In particular, both pseudonym and inspection predicates involve an increase of between 10 and 15 milliseconds for proving and verifying. Revocation is a bit more expensive, as it involves an extra showing of a credential (with only one attribute) plus the proof of equality of committed values. This takes around 30 milliseconds in total for each process. We remark that these overheads are constant (per predicate), so depending on the number of (hidden) attributes in the whole credential, they will constitute a different portion of the total proving and verifying time, but in no case meaningfully increase the magnitude of the process. This can be appreciated by comparing Figure 7a and Figure 7a, where the number of identity attributes in the credential was different. In the former, the number of hidden attributes is 4. This could be the case, for instance, of a simple electronic identification credential with name, date of birth, id and gender as attributes. For the latter, we use 10 hidden attributes, which could be the case for a deployment using eIDAS attributes¹¹.

Figure 7: Execution times for proving and verifying when applying each of the predicates introduced in Section 5 along with the basic policy as a reference point.

The corresponding results for the range predicates are shown in Figure 8. In contrast to the previous case, while the overhead is again constant, range proofs drastically increase the execution time. However, the execution time is not prohibitive, especially in the case of 16 and 32 bits proofs, which cover most use cases and take significantly less than 1 second to complete. The apparent effect of the size parameter is the

¹¹E.g., Given name, Family name, Identifier, Date of birth, Address (4 components), Gender and Place of birth, see https://docs.swedenconnect.se/technical-framework/mirror/eidas/eIDAS_SAML_Attribute_Profile_v1.2-FINAL.pdf

one expected from Bulletproofs [24]. Other solutions for proving range predicates will be similarly complex, and in many cases worse for one or both phases. This exemplifies the advantage of the credential trust model of our scenario brought up in Section 5.1: as the attributes were attested by the issuance authority, showing they are included in the credential rules out possible forgeries through modular arithmetic overflows, which otherwise would require an additional—and expensive—range proof.

Figure 8: Execution times for proving and verifying in i) Basic reveal policy (BRP), and BRP plus a range proof of ii) 16-bit range, iii) 32-bit range, iv) 64-bit range.

As with execution time, the impact on the final token size of adding one of the developed applications as part of a credential showing is constant. The specific values are summarized in Table 1, considering the use of 48 bytes for \mathbb{Z}_p elements and 97 bytes for \mathbb{G}_1 , as used in the implementation. Likewise, we show examples of token sizes for proofs with 4 and 10 hidden attributes, along with the effect of the linking commitment on that size. These values come from the formula that governs token size in our modified presentation methods: $2\mathbb{G}_1 + 3\mathbb{Z}_p + (h + 2p)\mathbb{Z}_p$, where h is the number of hidden attributes, and p is number of commitments linked to the credential. As an example, in a showing with a pseudonym and inspection predicate, plus 4 hidden attributes, the size of the proof sent to the verifier would be $2 \cdot 193 + 241 + 483 + 626 = 1736$ bytes.

	Linking commitment	Pseudonym	Inspection	Revocation	Range 16-bit	Range 32-bit	Range 64-bit	4 hidden attributes	10 hidden attributes
Elements	$1\mathbb{G}_1 + 2\mathbb{Z}_p$	$1\mathbb{G}_1 + 3\mathbb{Z}_p$	$3\mathbb{G}_1 + 4\mathbb{Z}_p$	$2\mathbb{G}_1 + 10\mathbb{Z}_p$	$12\mathbb{G}_1 + 5\mathbb{Z}_p$	$14\mathbb{G}_1 + 5\mathbb{Z}_p$	$16\mathbb{G}_1 + 5\mathbb{Z}_p$	$2\mathbb{G}_1 + 9\mathbb{Z}_p$	$2\mathbb{G}_1 + 15\mathbb{Z}_p$
Bytes	193	241	483	674	1404	1598	1792	626	914

Table 1: Overhead in token size of the different predicates, along with the size increase of the proof because of a linking commitment, and token sizes credential showings with 4 and 10 hidden attributes. Values correspond to using 48 and 97 bytes for \mathbb{Z}_p and \mathbb{G}_1 element representation.

6.2. Comparison with Idemix

570 We consider the Identity Mixer (*Idemix*) system as a comparison target because it is the only implementation in the literature that supports all predicates considered in this work, and it achieves a similarly modular approach. We use the public implementation of the Idemix library (version 3.0.36), as adopted in the H2020 project ARIES [60].

The results are shown in Figure 9. Idemix performs significantly worse in the basic policy scenario. In fact, its results are similar, and even worse, than those of our approach when a pseudonym, inspection, or revocation predicate is included in the policy. To further exemplify the difference, we also show the execution times for a policy with a pseudonym predicate. Again, we see that Idemix is much slower, especially during proof generation. We omit the case of range predicates for comparison as the bulk of the computation time comes from the range proof itself, which can be modularly changed in both cases. Even then, the base 580 computations for the credential would still be faster in our approach. What is more, the Idemix instantiation uses 2048 bit keys, basing its security on the RSA assumption, so it hardly achieves 112 bits of security [62], while the BLS-461 curve used in our approach enables around 134 bits of security.

Figure 9: Comparison of Idemix with our implementation from Sect. 5, both for a basic policy with statements for hiding/revealing attributes, and another with a pseudonym proof on top.

6.3. Additional feasibility results

To further exemplify the practicality of the developed approach, we tested it in two additional scenarios.

585 First, we deployed the code in a phone—as a simple Android application that uses the Java code library—to test its applicability in mobile scenarios. The hardware used was a Poco X3 NFC with a Qualcomm Snapdragon 732G octa-core 2.3GHz. The results (cf. Figure 10) show that the basic policy and inspection

and pseudonym predicates are well below one second for the full flow of proving and verification, while revocation would take around 1.2 seconds. These are fine values for usability in real time scenarios. However, range proofs are expensive enough to be too noticeable during a showing process, taking from ~ 5.5 to ~ 17 seconds for a full showing depending on the number of bits.

Nonetheless, in a real world context these results can be alleviated, and various optimizations are simple to apply. For instance, parts of the operations can be pre-computed and/or be partially hidden through user interaction with the application. For instance, a proper privacy-respecting authentication process involves an informed consent check, and operations can be carried out during the time it takes the user to complete that process. Moreover, in many applications, the verifier is not another phone, but a server which usually has powerful hardware, so the the increase in verification times would not be relevant. Lastly, the implementation can be optimized in multiple ways. One of them is using a C implementation for the cryptographic operations, which results in great improvements as shown in the remainder of the section. More concretely, depending on how expensive the computation is, the impact of implementing the cryptographic operations in C is a 5 to 10 times faster execution. In the 16 and 32 bit range cases, this would lead to around 1 second proving times, which are practical values, especially considering the possibility of precomputing during user interaction.

Figure 10: Execution times obtained for the different methods in a mobile phone.

The cryptographic operations account for most of the computational complexity, so it is useful to implement them in a fast, though less manageable, language like C. This can lead to considerable improvements in execution time, which helps when performance is very relevant or computing capabilities are reduced. To

demonstrate this, we tested the cryptographic operations for two sample flows that are common in practice: a basic reveal policy, and a scenario with pseudonyms and inspection. Apart from the Java implementation presented above, we used a C implementation that relies on the BLS12-381 curve, with an estimated security level slightly lower than 128 bits [63], relaxing the security threshold to acceptable levels to accommodate an environment with higher efficiency demands. Figure 11 shows the results for both implementations, with very clear performance improvements in the C implementation, with the all operations taking around 10 ms and 20 ms in the basic policy and pseudonym plus inspection scenarios, respectively.

Figure 11: Comparison between the Java and C implementation of our system in two example scenarios.

7. Conclusions

The prevalence of digital and online services demands the access to privacy-respecting identity management for authentication and authorization. Encouraged by regulations like GDPR and their data minimization and privacy-by-design goals, the self-sovereign identity paradigm is gaining the spotlight. In this scope, privacy-preserving Attribute Based Credentials (p-ABC) are a powerful tool to empower users. This is especially the case for fully distributed p-ABCs based on multi-signatures, which enable the decentralization of the issuance process, fully inline with the SSI principles. In this work, we introduce an extended distributed p-ABC system that offers the usual minimal disclosure and unlinkability properties, along with modular extensions of functionality, achieving in particular range proofs, inspection, pseudonyms and revocation. This is the only implementation of such a system. We evaluate the implementation and prove its practicability in various scenarios, and show how it heavily outperforms Idemix, the only implementation with equivalent functionality and extensibility.

From the work in this paper, some avenues for future developments are still possible. First, research on advanced issuance techniques, e.g., issuance on hidden attributes, that complement the enhanced showing

phase results of this paper is an interesting topic. Then, research on proofs in the commit-and-prove paradigm would, apart from the value of the contribution in itself, automatically improve the system presented in this work. Lastly, implementation efforts, like extending the C library with range proofs, would open up new scenarios like traditional devices and IoT coexistence in a domain. Such domains with constrained devices have suffered a lack of privacy-preserving identity management because of poor efficiency or flexibility.

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Scenario	Experiment	Phase	Mean	SD	Experiment	Phase	Mean	SD	
Execution on a laptop: 4 hidden attributes	Basic reveal policy (BRP)	<i>Proving</i>	27.90	2.49	Pseudonym	<i>Proving</i>	38.53	1.18	
		<i>Verifying</i>	29.73	2.31		<i>Verifying</i>	39.93	1.29	
	Inspection (no CCA)	<i>Proving</i>	40.37	1.28	Revocation	<i>Proving</i>	59.63	1.99	
		<i>Verifying</i>	40.70	1.46		<i>Verifying</i>	60.03	1.35	
	Range16bits (1 proof)	<i>Proving</i>	348.33	2.90	Range32bits (1 proof)	<i>Proving</i>	606.60	3.37	
		<i>Verifying</i>	192.70	1.64		<i>Verifying</i>	308.33	2.70	
	Range64bits (1 proof)	<i>Proving</i>	1089.20	6.38	Pseudonym+Inspection	<i>Proving</i>	53.00	1.15	
		<i>Verifying</i>	538.20	6.05		<i>Verifying</i>	55.03	1.20	
Execution on a laptop: 10 hidden attributes	Basic reveal policy (BRP)	<i>Proving</i>	37.20	1.35	Pseudonym	<i>Proving</i>	48.30	0.97	
		<i>Verifying</i>	38.13	1.45		<i>Verifying</i>	49.43	1.05	
	Inspection (no CCA)	<i>Proving</i>	51.40	1.17	Revocation	<i>Proving</i>	70.60	1.93	
		<i>Verifying</i>	50.73	1.24		<i>Verifying</i>	70.03	1.47	
Execution on a mobile phone	Basic reveal policy (BRP)	<i>Proving</i>	262.20	2.64	Pseudonym	<i>Proving</i>	395.30	1.68	
		<i>Verifying</i>	277.10	1.97		<i>Verifying</i>	412.10	2.30	
	Inspection (no CCA)	<i>Proving</i>	417.50	2.80	Revocation	<i>Proving</i>	605.10	1.51	
		<i>Verifying</i>	421.90	1.64		<i>Verifying</i>	618.30	1.90	
	Range16bits (1 proof)	<i>Proving</i>	3733.50	5.41	Range32bits (1 proof)	<i>Proving</i>	6606.60	218.58	
		<i>Verifying</i>	2071.00	5.04		<i>Verifying</i>	3359.20	102.49	
	Range64bits (1 proof)	<i>Proving</i>	11788.00	15.00					
		<i>Verifying</i>	5855.50	15.50					
Idemix	BRP	<i>Proving</i>	78.07	1.60	Pseudonym	<i>Proving</i>	166.34	1.30	
		<i>Verifying</i>	57.94	1.49		<i>Verifying</i>	62.04	0.59	
C cryptographic implementation	Basic reveal policy (BRP)	<i>Proving</i>	5.07	0.45	Pseudonym+Inspection	<i>Proving</i>	10.73	0.68	
		<i>Verifying</i>	5.45	0.62		<i>Verifying</i>	10.04	0.34	

Table A.2: Results of the experiments in the various scenarios detailed in Section 6, measured in milliseconds